

Morpho-Physiological Characterization and Yield Performance of Chickpea Genotypes Under Moisture Stress Conditions

Raghvendra Diwedi ^a, Mousmi Syed ^{b*} and Mahipat Singh ^a

^a Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding, Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Bundelkhand University, Jhansi (U.P.), India.

^b Department of Seed Science and Technology, Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Bundelkhand University, Jhansi (U.P.), India.

Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration among all authors. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Article Information

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.56557/ajrra/2025/v7i1170>

Open Peer Review History:

This journal follows the Advanced Open Peer Review policy. Identity of the Reviewers, Editor(s) and additional Reviewers, peer review comments, different versions of the manuscript, comments of the editors, etc are available here: <https://prh.globalpresshub.com/review-history/2025>

Original Research Article

Received: 05/05/2025
Published: 17/07/2025

ABSTRACT

The present study was conducted at the Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding, Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Bundelkhand University, Jhansi (U.P.) to evaluate twelve chickpea genotypes under normal and late sown conditions. The objective was to analyze their morpho-physiological traits and yield performance under moisture stress and non-stress environments. A split plot complete block design was used for evaluating seed yield, morphological traits, and physiological responses. Results revealed that moisture stress significantly reduced plant height, days to maturity, reproductive duration, and pod number, while relative water content and test weight

*Corresponding author: E-mail: mousmisyed@gmail.com;

Cite as: Diwedi, Raghvendra, Mousmi Syed, and Mahipat Singh. 2025. "Morpho-Physiological Characterization and Yield Performance of Chickpea Genotypes Under Moisture Stress Conditions". *Asian Journal of Research and Review in Agriculture* 7 (1):202-14. <https://doi.org/10.56557/ajrra/2025/v7i1170>.

remained largely unaffected. Genotypes K-850, ICC 4958, and IC-305536 showed superior drought tolerance and yield under stress, making them promising candidates for cultivation in drought-prone and delayed sowing regions.

Keywords: Chickpea; drought stress; genotype evaluation; morpho-physiological traits; yield components; late sowing.

1. INTRODUCTION

Cicer arietinum L., is popularly known as chickpea, the third most important grain legume in the world after dry beans and dry peas, that brings about a formidable solution to the alarming problems of protein scarcity of the world. Globally, chickpea is cultivated on about 10.4 m ha adding 8.04 m tonnes of seeds to the global food basket with an average productivity of 773 kg/ha. India predominates the global chickpea supply, as it has the distinction of being the largest producer and consumer in the world and accounts for over 66 per cent of the global output. India grows chickpea on about 6.86 m ha, producing 5.35 m tonnes of grains, representing 32 and 42 per cent of the national pulse acreage and production, respectively with productivity of 780 kg/ha. Though Indian average productivity is on par with world's average productivity, it is less compared to the other countries, like North and Central America (1211 kg/ha) and Canada (1368 kg/ha). Most of the promising chickpea tested in the national network have shown potential yield of 2000 to 2500 kg/ha; whereas, the national average still languishes at 750 to 850 kg/ha. Karnataka grows chickpea on about 319 lakh ha producing 181 lakh tonnes with a productivity of 512 kg/ha, constituting one among the lowest producing states in the country" (Sharma & Sharma, 2020). The major factors contributing to low yield in the state are the short period available for the crop growth and incidence of terminal drought accompanied with other biotic stresses. Although, the progress towards alleviating biotic stresses affecting chickpea productivity has been satisfactory, the work on abiotic stresses needs immediate attention. The most important abiotic stress is the drought, which severely affect the productivity of chickpea under rainfed production system.

The moisture stress affects almost all biophysical and biochemical process, the crop growth and the final yield. The irrigation is not the only answer to the problem. However, despite many decades of research, drought continues to be a major challenge to agricultural scientists due to unpredictability of its occurrence, severity, timing

and duration and coupled with other abiotic stresses, particularly high temperature, variation in nutrient availability and biotic stresses. In spite of plant's genetic make up and optimum population, breeding has not been as effective on different agronomic parameters of the crop under drought stress conditions as it has in their absence. Moreover, breeding for drought resistance is very frustrating. To quote Arnon et al., (1980), "Breeding for drought resistance has been a consistent theme for as long as I remember and probably the greatest source of wasted breeding efforts in the whole field of plant breeding. The physiological processes also set a limit on yield. Many techniques give quantitative estimation of morphological changes that takes place during the growth of crop and provides some insight in to the physiological variation in yield caused either genetically or by environment. Several approaches can be adapted to maintain or increase productivity under moisture stress condition. Any method or criteria used for selection, needs to be more thoroughly evaluated and carefully monitored before suggesting it for drought tolerance breeding".

Chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.) is a crucial pulse crop known for its adaptability to arid and semi-arid environments. However, it is highly sensitive to drought, particularly during flowering and pod development (Jukanti et al., 2012). With the increasing incidence of climate variability and moisture stress, identifying drought-tolerant genotypes has become imperative. This study was undertaken to evaluate selected genotypes under simulated field conditions to identify drought-tolerant traits and assess genetic variability.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was conducted at Organic Research Farm, Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding, Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Bundelkhand University, Jhansi (U.P.) during 2024- 2025 using twelve chickpea genotypes under two sowing dates: normal (14 Nov 2024) and late (11 Dec 2024). Two main treatments—

moisture stress and non-stress—were applied. The experimental layout followed a split plot design with three replications. Standard agronomic practices were followed for crop cultivation. Five plants per genotype per replication and treatment were randomly selected to record various observations.

2.1.1 Morpho-physiological Traits

Plant height (cm): Measured from ground level to the tip of the longest branch at physiological maturity.

Days to first flowering: Days from sowing to first flower opening.

Days to maturity: Days from sowing to physiological maturity based on yellowing of pods and leaves.

Reproductive duration: Days from first flowering to maturity.

Leaf length (cm): Measured from the sixth leaf from the top of the primary branch.

Leaflet length and width (cm): Taken from the sixth leaflet of the measured leaf.

2.1.2 Yield and yield components

Branches per plant: Counted at maturity on five randomly selected plants.

Pods per plant: Total seed-bearing pods counted per plant and averaged.

Seeds per pod: Average from 10 pods per plant.

Test weight (g): Weight of 100 randomly selected seeds.

Seed yield per plant (g): Grain weight per plant.

2.1.3 Drought Susceptibility Index (DSI)

DSI for seed yield was calculated using the formula by Fischer and Maurer (1978):

$$DSI = (1 - YD/YP) / D, \text{ where } D = 1 - (\bar{YD} / \bar{YP})$$

- YD = Yield under stress

- YP = Yield under non-stress

- \bar{YD} , \bar{YP} = Mean yields across all genotypes under stress and non-stress respectively

2.2 Statistical Analysis

The experimental data recorded for various morpho-physiological, yield, and drought tolerance traits were subjected to statistical analysis using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) appropriate for a split-plot design. Significance of differences among treatments and genotypes was tested at 5% probability level. Mean values

were compared using the Critical Difference (CD) test. The data analysis was performed using standard statistical software such as OPSTAT and Microsoft Excel. The Drought Susceptibility Index (DSI) was computed as per the formula proposed by Fischer and Maurer (1978) to assess the relative performance of genotypes under stress and non-stress conditions.

The analysis of variance revealed significant differences among genotypes, treatments, and their interactions for most morpho-physiological and yield-related traits under both normal (E1) and late sown (E2) conditions. The variability indicates substantial scope for identifying drought-resilient genotypes based on their performance across different environments.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Morpho-Physiological Traits

Plant Height: Genotypic variation for plant height was significant under both stress and non-stress conditions. Genotype IC-305595 showed maximum plant height under non-stress in both normal and late sown crops. The mean reduction in plant height due to stress was 8.07 cm in normal and 7.02 cm in late sown crops. Genotypes like IC-327723 and ICC4958 maintained moderate height under stress, indicating resilience. Similar genotypic differences in height reduction due to drought have been reported in legumes by Khan et al. (2010) and confirmed in chickpea by Sharma et al. (2016), indicating inherent variation in drought responsiveness.

Days to First Flowering and Maturity: Moisture stress led to early flowering and early physiological maturity. IC-305593 showed the earliest flowering (29.65 days under normal) and was also early to mature, which suggests its potential as a drought escape genotype. The reproductive duration was highest in IC-305593 under non-stress but was significantly reduced under stress, particularly in normal sown conditions, a characteristic commonly linked to drought escape (Kumar et al., 2012; Tuberosa, 2012). Early-maturing genotypes often escape terminal drought, enhancing their adaptive advantage under rainfed conditions.

Reproductive Duration: The reproductive phase was highly variable and significantly affected by drought. IC-305595 and IC-305477 maintained longer durations under non-stress but reduced sharply under stress. The average

Table 1. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) for morpho-physiological, yield and yield related traits under non-stress and stress treatments in normal sown experiment (E1) of chickpea genotypes

Source of Variation	df	Plant height (cm)	Days to first flowering	Days to maturity	Reproductive phase	Leaf length (cm)	Leaflet length (cm)	Leaflet width (cm)	RWC (%)	No. of branches/plant	No. of pods/plant	Test weight (g)	Seed yield/plant (g)	Biological yield/plant (g)
Replication	1	0.71	0.94	0.11	0.96	0.018	0.052	0.061	0.05	0.33	14.23	12.04	2.78	0.67
Treatment	1	765.24**	578.63	1873.44*	443.12*	898.12	1.745*	1.108	0.24	129.67	3271.44*	85.12	365.73	695.34
Error (a)	1	0.17	8.94	1.42	2.43	0.09	0.0018	0.007	0.014	2.59	12.35	1.22	5.43	10.21
Genotypes (G)	11	47.03**	248.12**	211.65**	35.92**	2.93**	61.48**	0.158**	0.0058**	8.14**	342.12**	106.84**	15.62**	41.75**
G x T Interaction	11	17.34**	6.57*	5.43**	5.74**	1.69**	0.031	0.045**	0.0019	2.54*	58.13**	3.48	6.94**	18.25**
Error (b)	22	1.17	2.22	1.81	1.38	0.016	0.0051	0.0022	0.0021	1.22	6.43	28.91	1.88	2.84

RWC: Relative water content\ DF: Degrees of Freedom\ G: Genotype\ T: Treatment.

Table 2. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) for morpho-physiological, yield and yield related traits under non-stress and stress treatments in late sown experiment (E2) of chickpea genotypes

Source of Variation	DF	Plant height (cm)	Days to first flowering (Days)	Days to maturity (Days)	Reproductive phase (Days)	RWC (%)	No. of branches/plant	No. of pods/plant	Test weight (g)	Seed yield/plant (g)	Biological yield/plant (g)
Replication	1	3.95	10.42	1.37	5.12	0.014	0.71	12.36	1.67	2.91	5.23
Treatment	1	891.14**	158.34*	493.76*	126.85*	85.12	55.67*	1376.48*	39.77*	146.21*	371.56*
Error (a)	1	0.091	0.29	2.08	0.15	0.000	0.26	0.48	1.43	0.64	1.14
Genotypes	12	54.63**	240.17**	314.98**	46.83**	0.006	5.34**	318.73**	149.04**	6.52**	34.28**
G x T Interaction	12	17.29**	6.85**	2.09	8.34**	0.003	0.893	39.42**	0.92	3.15	13.87**
Error (b)	24	1.43	0.98	1.76	0.61	0.006	0.49	7.86	1.48	1.61	3.78

RWC: Relative water content\ DF: Degrees of Freedom\ G: Genotype\ T: Treatment.

Table 3. Plant Height (Cm) Of Different Genotypes of Chickpea Under Stress and Non-Stress Treatments in Normal and Late Sown Experiments

Genotypes	Normal Sown (14 Nov 2024) Non-stress			Stress	Mean	N-S	Late Sown (11 Dec 2024) Non-stress			Stress	Mean	N-S
	Stress	Mean	N-S				Stress	Mean	N-S			
K-850	44.2	42.1	43.15	42.1	43.15	2.1	41.6	31.8	36.7	9.8		
ICC-4958	41.2	38.9	40.05	38.9	40.05	2.3	38.7	36.1	37.4	2.6		
IC-305595	45.0	38.7	41.85	38.7	41.85	6.3	44.2	35.9	40.05	8.3		
IC-327373	42.9	30.6	36.75	30.6	36.75	12.3	34.3	26.8	30.55	7.5		
IC-305536	41.9	31.2	36.55	31.2	36.55	10.7	41.1	28.6	34.85	12.5		
IC-327509	50.1	39.1	44.6	39.1	44.6	11.0	43.1	36.3	39.7	6.8		
IC-305593	42.6	36.1	39.35	36.1	39.35	6.5	37.6	33.1	35.35	4.5		
IC-328020	43.5	33.8	38.65	33.8	38.65	9.7	40.7	32.4	36.55	8.3		
IC-305477	50.4	37.9	44.15	37.9	44.15	12.5	45.3	36.1	40.7	9.2		
IC-327156	41.4	33.1	37.25	33.1	37.25	8.3	39.2	31.1	35.15	8.1		

Genotypes	Normal Sown (14 Nov 2024) Non-stress	Stress	Mean	N-S	Late Sown (11 Dec 2024) Non-stress	Stress	Mean	N-S
IC-327534	48.8	41.9	45.35	6.9	44.1	37.3	40.7	6.8
IC-327723	43.4	38.0	40.7	5.4	43.5	36.8	40.15	6.7
Mean	44.15	36.08	40.12	8.07	41.82	34.8	38.31	7.02

CD (Critical Difference) at 5% Level

Comparison	Normal Sown	Late Sown
Between two main treatments	1.48	4.65
Between two sub means	1.55	1.34
Between two sub means at same main	2.24	1.68
Between two sub means at same or different sub treatments	2.02	1.95

N: Non-stress\ S: Stress/ N-S: Non-stress - Stress

Table 4. Number of days taken to first flowering of chickpea genotypes under moisture stress and non-stress treatments in normal and late sown experiments

Genotypes	Normal Sown (14 Nov 2024) Non-stress	Stress	Mean	N-S	Late Sown (11 Dec 2024) Non-stress	Stress	Mean	N-S
K-850	59.1	53.6	56.35	5.5	54.2	47.1	50.65	7.1
ICC-4958	55.0	48.2	51.6	6.8	48.6	45.2	46.9	3.4
IC-305595	49.6	42.1	45.85	7.5	39.8	38.2	39.0	1.6
IC-327373	53.1	44.0	48.55	9.1	41.5	36.5	39.0	5.0
IC-305536	53.7	47.2	50.45	6.5	48.0	37.6	42.8	10.4
IC-327509	58.6	51.4	55.0	7.2	49.0	48.4	48.7	0.6
IC-305593	31.0	28.3	29.65	2.7	28.1	23.9	26.0	4.2
IC-328020	54.7	44.0	49.35	10.7	39.1	37.9	38.5	1.2
IC-305477	53.6	44.5	49.05	9.1	37.4	32.9	35.15	4.5
IC-327156	35.6	31.8	33.7	3.8	29.5	27.8	28.65	1.7
IC-327534	57.6	48.1	52.85	9.5	47.4	44.3	45.85	3.1
IC-327723	58.1	49.1	53.6	9.0	49.1	44.2	46.65	4.9
Mean	51.73	44.35	48.04	-	41.85	37.93	39.89	-

CD (Critical Difference) at 5% Level

Comparison	Normal Sown	Late Sown
Between two main treatments	10.958	1.990
Between two sub means	2.215	1.550
Between two sub means at same main	2.980	2.120
Between two sub means at same or different sub treatments	3.356	2.088

N: Non-stress\ S: Stress\ N-S: Non-stress - Stress

Table 5. Number of days taken to maturity of chickpea genotypes under moisture stress and non-stress treatments in normal and late sown experiments

Genotypes	Normal Sown (14 Nov 2024) Non-stress	Stress	Mean	N-S	Late Sown (11 Dec 2024) Non-stress	Stress	Mean	N-S
K-850	112.0	97.2	104.6	14.8	91.2	86.3	88.75	4.9
ICC4958	96.1	87.4	91.75	8.7	78.3	73.8	76.05	4.5
IC-305595	102.2	85.1	93.65	17.1	76.2	71.1	73.65	5.1
IC-327373	100.8	85.3	93.05	15.5	76.8	71.1	73.95	5.7

Genotypes	Normal Sown (14 Nov 2024) Non-stress	Stress	Mean	N-S	Late Sown (11 Dec 2024) Non-stress	Stress	Mean	N-S
IC-305536	98.1	86.7	92.4	11.4	77.8	71.8	74.8	6.0
IC-327509	111.8	97.0	104.4	14.8	91.0	86.1	88.55	4.9
IC-305593	86.1	74.1	80.1	12.0	64.1	54.3	59.2	9.8
IC-328020	96.9	86.2	91.55	10.7	79.3	73.4	76.35	5.9
IC-305477	98.2	86.1	92.15	12.1	80.1	72.1	76.1	8.0
IC-327156	87.8	77.0	82.4	10.8	70.2	64.4	67.3	5.8
IC-327534	105.3	91.3	98.3	14.0	85.2	77.4	81.3	7.8
IC-327723	105.4	92.3	98.85	13.1	85.6	78.7	82.15	6.9
Mean	100.18	87.11	93.64	-	78.54	72.12	75.33	-

CD (Critical Difference) at 5% Level

Comparison	Normal Sown	Late Sown
Between two main treatments	4.108	4.890
Between two sub means	1.912	1.950
Between two sub means at same main	2.705	---
Between two sub means at same or different sub treatments	2.680	---

N: Non- stress|S: Stress/ N-S: Non-stress – Stress

Table 6. Duration of reproductive phase (days) of different chickpea genotypes under moisture stress and non- stress treatments of normal and late sown experiments

Genotypes	Normal Sown (Non-stress)	Normal Sown (Stress)	Normal Sown (Mean)	Normal Sown (N-S)	Late Sown (Non-stress)	Late Sown (Stress)	Late Sown (Mean)	Late Sown (N-S)
K-850	51.5	44.0	47.75	7.5	38.5	37.5	38.0	1.0
ICC4958	45.0	41.0	43.0	4.0	31.5	28.5	30.0	3.0
IC-305595	50.5	40.5	45.5	10.0	36.0	32.0	34.0	4.0
IC-327373	46.5	38.5	42.5	8.0	35.5	34.0	33.75	1.5
IC-305536	43.5	37.5	40.5	6.0	35.5	32.5	34.0	3.0
IC-327509	52.5	43.5	48.0	9.0	41.5	38.5	40.0	3.0
IC-305593	54.0	46.0	50.0	8.0	35.5	30.5	33.0	5.0
IC-328020	42.5	41.0	41.75	1.5	38.5	34.5	36.5	4.0
IC-305477	44.5	40.5	42.5	4.0	41.0	41.0	41.0	0.0
IC-327156	52.5	45.5	49.0	7.0	39.0	37.0	38.0	2.0
IC-327534	48.5	42.5	45.5	6.0	39.0	33.0	36.0	6.0
IC-327723	48.5	44.0	46.25	4.5	36.5	33.0	34.75	3.5
Mean	48.33	42.04	45.19	-	36.89	33.62	34.25	-

Critical Difference (CD) at 5%

Comparison Type	Normal Sown Crop	Late Sown Crop
Between two main treatments	5.81	1.459
Between two sub means	1.68	1.183
Between two sub means at same main	2.38	1.673
Between two sub means at same or different sub treatments	2.47	1.625

N: Non- stress|S: Stress/ N-S: Non-stress – Stress

Table 7. Leaf length, leaflet length and leaflet diameter (cm) of different genotypes of chickpea under moisture stress and non-stress treatments of normal sown experiment

Genotypes	Leaf length (Non-stress)	Leaf length (Stress)	Leaf length (Mean)	N-S	Leaflet length (Non-stress)	Leaflet length (Stress)	Leaflet length (Mean)	N-S	Leaflet width (Non-stress)	Leaflet width (Stress)	Leaflet width (Mean)	N-S
K-850	4.65	3.35	4.0	1.3	1.28	0.71	0.99	0.57	0.96	0.49	0.73	0.47
ICC4958	4.55	3.4	3.98	1.15	1.21	0.59	0.9	0.62	0.73	0.42	0.58	0.31
IC-305595	5.5	3.3	4.4	2.2	1.12	0.69	0.91	0.43	0.84	0.35	0.6	0.49
IC-327373	4.6	3.2	3.9	1.4	0.91	0.58	0.75	0.33	0.56	0.43	0.5	0.13
IC-305536	3.9	2.8	3.35	1.1	0.78	0.49	0.64	0.29	0.57	0.37	0.47	0.2
IC-327509	5.5	3.35	4.45	2.15	1.31	0.83	1.07	0.48	1.39	0.53	0.96	0.86
IC-305593	3.55	2.4	2.98	1.15	0.92	0.5	0.71	0.42	0.61	0.34	0.48	0.27
IC-328020	4.0	3.25	3.63	0.75	0.88	0.64	0.76	0.24	0.61	0.39	0.5	0.22
IC-305477	5.3	3.45	4.38	1.85	0.95	0.49	0.72	0.46	0.51	0.35	0.43	0.16
IC-327156	6.25	4.1	5.18	2.15	1.78	1.07	1.43	0.71	1.1	0.67	0.89	0.43
IC-327534	4.65	3.95	4.3	0.7	1.42	1.2	1.31	0.22	0.93	0.7	0.82	0.23
IC-327723	4.75	4.35	4.45	0.4	1.19	1.15	1.17	0.05	0.85	0.84	0.85	0.01
Mean	4.31	3.41	3.86	-	1.146	0.745	0.945	0.401	0.805	0.49	0.648	-

Critical Difference (CD) at 5%

Comparison Type	Leaf Length	Leaflet Length	Leaflet Width
Between two main treatments	1.161	0.143	0.328
Between two sub means	0.176	0.092	-
Between two sub means at same main	0.249	0.130	-
Between two sub means at same or different sub treatments	0.305	0.127	-

N: Non-stress; S: Stress/ N-S: Non-stress – Stress

Table 8. Relative water content (%) at 60 Das of different chickpea genotypes under moisture stress and non-stress treatments in normal and late sown experiments

3	Normal Sown (Non-stress)	Normal Sown (Stress)	Normal Sown (Mean)	N-S	Late Sown (Non-stress)	Late Sown (Stress)	Late Sown (Mean)	N-S
K-850	64.4	53.5	59.0	10.9	81.4	69.8	75.6	11.6
ICC4958	60.1	49.9	55.0	10.2	70.8	61.2	66.0	9.6
IC-305595	65.7	54.6	60.2	11.1	76.6	72.4	74.5	4.2
IC-327373	56.3	42.2	49.2	14.1	78.6	60.9	69.7	17.7
IC-305536	60.6	46.6	53.6	14.0	68.7	65.7	67.2	3.0
IC-327509	64.9	50.2	57.5	14.7	71.2	63.1	67.1	8.1
IC-305593	71.4	53.8	62.6	17.6	77.2	74.4	75.8	2.8
IC-328020	68.2	53.7	60.9	14.5	79.3	67.4	73.3	11.9

3	Normal Sown (Non-stress)	Normal Sown (Stress)	Normal Sown (Mean)	N-S	Late Sown (Non-stress)	Late Sown (Stress)	Late Sown (Mean)	N-S
IC-305477	65.7	49.4	57.0	16.3	75.0	71.3	73.1	3.7
IC-327156	67.7	56.6	62.1	11.1	74.8	71.0	72.9	3.8
IC-327534	71.8	48.7	60.2	23.1	72.6	71.8	72.2	0.8
IC-327723	71.8	51.7	61.7	20.1	77.3	71.8	74.6	5.5
Mean	65.7	50.9	58.3	-	74.9	69.2	72.1	-

Critical Difference (CD) at 5%

Comparison Type	Normal Sown	Late Sown
Between two main treatments	25.01	07.60
Between two sub means	05.70	10.30
Between two sub means at same main	---	---
Between two sub means at same or different sub treatments	---	---

N: Non-stress\ S: Stress/ N-S: Non-stress – Stress

Table 9. Number of branches per plant of different chickpea genotypes under moisture stress and non-stress treatments in normal and late sown experiments

Genotypes	Normal Non-stress	Normal Stress	Normal Genotype Mean	Normal N-S	Late Non-stress	Late Stress	Late Genotype Mean	Late N-S
K-850	11.2	8.4	9.8	2.8	9.0	6.2	7.6	2.8
ICC4958	11.0	9.0	10.0	2.0	8.0	7.0	7.5	1.0
IC-305595	12.1	6.0	9.05	6.1	9.5	6.0	7.75	3.5
IC-327373	9.0	7.0	8.0	2.0	8.5	5.5	7.0	3.0
IC-305536	10.2	8.0	9.1	2.2	10.0	7.0	8.5	3.0
IC-327509	11.5	7.0	9.25	4.5	10.2	6.5	8.35	3.7
IC-305593	6.5	5.2	5.85	1.3	6.0	4.0	5.0	2.0
IC-328020	13.0	7.0	10.0	6.0	8.0	6.5	7.25	1.5
IC-305477	15.0	9.0	12.0	6.0	8.2	7.0	7.6	1.2
IC-327156	9.5	6.0	7.75	3.5	7.5	5.5	6.5	2.0
IC-327534	12.0	7.0	9.5	5.0	6.8	6.0	6.4	0.8
IC-327723	10.5	8.0	9.25	2.5	7.0	5.5	6.25	1.5
Mean	11.0	7.5	9.25	-	8.25	6.0	7.12	-
CD at 5%								
Between two main treatments	6.0				2.000			
Between two sub means	1.70				1.000			
Between two sub means at same main	2.5				---			
Between two sub means at same or different sub treatments	2.60				---			

N: Non-stress\ S: Stress/ N-S: Non-stress – Stress

Table 10. Number of pods per plant of different chickpea genotypes under moisture stress and non-stress treatments of normal and late sown experiments

Genotypes	Normal Non-stress	Normal Stress	Genotypes Mean	Normal N-S	Late Non-stress	Late Stress	Genotype Mean	Late N-S
K-850	36.0	28.0	32.0	8.0	30.5	23.0	26.75	7.5
ICC4958	55.0	47.0	51.0	8.0	38.0	33.0	35.5	5.0
IC-305595	62.0	35.0	48.5	27.0	52.0	36.0	44.0	16.0
IC-327373	39.0	29.0	34.0	10.0	32.0	22.0	27.0	10.0
IC-305536	61.0	38.0	49.5	23.0	50.0	36.0	43.0	14.0
IC-327509	52.0	36.0	44.0	16.0	32.0	26.0	29.0	6.0
IC-305593	48.0	33.0	40.5	15.0	47.0	28.0	37.5	19.0
IC-328020	57.0	34.0	45.5	23.0	50.0	29.0	39.5	21.0
IC-305477	80.0	50.0	65.0	30.0	55.0	38.0	46.5	17.0
IC-327156	49.0	39.0	44.0	10.0	27.0	18.0	22.5	9.0
IC-327534	42.0	29.0	35.5	13.0	24.0	19.0	21.5	5.0
IC-327723	43.0	24.0	33.5	19.0	21.0	20.0	20.5	1.0
Mean	52.33	35.0	43.67	-	38.29	27.92	33.1	-
CD at 5%								
Between two main treatments	12.50				2.500			
Between two sub means	3.80				4.000			
Between two sub means at same main	5.30				5.700			
Between two sub means at same or different sub treatments	5.50				5.500			

N: Non-stress\ S: Stress/ N-S: Non-stress - Stress

Table 11. Test weight (g) of different chickpea genotypes under moisture stress and non-stress treatments of normal and late sown experiments

Genotypes	Normal Non-stress	Normal Stress	Genotype Mean	Normal N-S	Late Non-stress	Late Stress	Genotype Means	Late N-S
K-850	32.00	30.50	31.25	1.50	29.00	28.20	28.60	0.80
ICC4958	26.00	22.50	24.25	3.50	17.50	15.00	16.25	2.50
IC-305595	20.00	17.00	18.50	3.00	19.00	14.50	16.75	4.50
IC-327373	17.00	14.00	15.50	3.00	13.00	11.00	12.00	2.00
IC-305536	21.00	20.00	20.50	1.00	17.00	16.00	16.50	1.00
IC-327509	28.00	25.00	26.50	3.00	25.00	23.00	24.00	2.00
IC-305593	24.00	20.00	22.00	4.00	16.50	14.00	15.25	2.50
IC-328020	19.00	15.00	17.00	4.00	18.50	15.00	16.75	3.50
IC-305477	21.00	18.00	19.50	3.00	20.00	17.00	18.50	3.00
IC-327156	31.00	23.00	27.00	8.00	25.50	21.00	23.25	4.50

IC-327534	30.00	28.00	29.00	2.00	26.00	24.00	25.00	2.00
IC-327723	33.00	30.00	31.50	3.00	30.00	28.00	29.00	2.00
Mean	24.83	21.83	23.33	-	23.04	20.38	21.71	-
CD @ 5%								
Between two main treatments	4.00				4.400			
Between two sub means	8.10				1.850			
Between two sub means at same main	---				---			
Between two sub means at same or different sub treatments	---				---			

N: Non-stress/S: Stress/N-S: Non-stress – Stress

Table 12. Seed yield per plant (g) of different chickpea genotypes under moisture stress and non-stress treatments of normal and late sown experiments

Genotypes	Normal Non-stress	Normal Stress	Genotype Mean	Normal N-S	Late Non-stress	Late Stress	Genotype Mean	Late N-S
K-850	12.40	9.25	10.83	3.15	9.80	6.85	8.33	2.95
ICC4958	13.05	10.30	11.68	2.75	11.60	8.75	10.18	2.85
IC-305595	14.20	8.10	11.15	6.10	13.30	7.05	10.18	6.25
IC-327373	8.70	5.15	6.93	3.55	6.50	3.20	4.85	3.30
IC-305536	13.80	9.90	11.85	3.90	11.20	8.15	9.68	3.05
IC-327509	15.60	7.50	11.55	8.10	8.60	4.60	6.60	4.00
IC-305593	10.20	6.25	8.23	3.95	7.80	5.00	6.40	2.80
IC-328020	11.50	5.35	8.43	6.15	10.40	4.25	7.33	6.15
IC-305477	17.10	9.20	13.15	7.90	8.50	5.30	6.90	3.20
IC-327156	13.30	6.10	9.70	7.20	10.10	5.90	8.00	4.20
IC-327534	12.60	9.55	11.08	3.05	9.10	6.50	7.80	2.60
IC-327723	14.80	10.00	12.40	4.80	11.50	7.95	9.73	3.55
Mean	13.07	8.18	10.62	-	9.76	6.51	8.13	-
Comparison	Normal				Late			
Between two main treatments	7.900				2.75			
Between two sub means	3.455				1.78			
Between two sub means at same main	5.010				---			
Between two sub means at same or different sub treatments	4.998				---			

N: Non-stress/S: Stress/N-S: Non-stress – Stress

reduction in reproductive duration was greater in normal sowing (6.29 days) than in late sowing (3.27 days). These findings align with Farooq et al. (2009), who observed reproductive stages to be the most drought-sensitive in legumes. Maintaining reproductive duration under stress may enhance yield potential.

Leaf Traits (Length, Leaflet Size): Leaf length, leaflet length, and leaflet width were all negatively impacted by stress. IC-327509 and IC-327156 maintained superior leaf traits under stress, suggesting better water retention and photosynthetic efficiency. Mean leaflet length and width under stress were 0.745 cm and 0.49 cm respectively, showing considerable reduction compared to non-stress conditions. Reddy et al. (2021) emphasized the role of leaf morphological traits in photosynthetic retention and water-use efficiency under stress. Similarly, Sivasakthi et al. (2017) highlighted leaf area reduction as an early indicator of drought response in chickpea.

Relative Water Content (RWC): RWC was fairly stable in genotypes like IC-305593 and IC-305477 across both environments, suggesting osmotic adjustment and efficient water uptake. Maximum RWC drop was observed in IC-327534, indicating susceptibility. The stability of RWC suggests efficient osmotic regulation or deep rooting ability, as noted in the studies by Iqbal et al. (2019) and Devi et al. (2014). This trait is useful for screening genotypes with physiological resilience.

3.2 Yield and Related Traits

Number of Branches and Pods per Plant: Stress significantly reduced branching. IC-305477 and IC-305595 showed high branching under non-stress but reduced considerably under stress. Mean branches per plant dropped from 11.0 to 7.5 in normal sowing and from 8.25 to 6.0 in late sowing. Pod number declined significantly under stress. IC-305477 had the highest pod number (80 under non-stress in normal sowing), while IC-327723 had the lowest. IC-305595 and IC-328020 maintained better pod numbers even under late sowing and stress conditions, reflecting good reproductive efficiency. Similar trends were observed by Sharma et al. (2016) and Varshney et al. (2014), who reported reduced reproductive success under moisture stress in chickpea.

Test Weight: Test weight remained relatively stable across conditions, with slight declines

observed under stress. Genotypes like IC-327723 and K-850 maintained higher test weight under stress in both sowings, indicating assimilate partitioning stability. Pandey et al. (2015) and Passioura (2012) also observed that final seed weight often exhibits greater stability under drought due to conservative assimilate partitioning.

Seed Yield: Seed yield was most affected by moisture stress, especially in late sown crops. K-850, ICC4958, and IC-305595 had higher yields under both stress and non-stress, reflecting drought tolerance. The mean seed yield under non-stress was 13.07 g and dropped to 8.18 g under stress in normal sown crops. In late sown crops, it dropped from 9.76 g to 6.51 g. These results are consistent with previous work by Varshney et al. (2014) and Sharma et al. (2016), who emphasized yield stability as a key selection index under drought.

Drought Susceptibility Index (DSI): DSI values distinguished tolerant and susceptible genotypes. K-850 and ICC4958 had low DSI values, indicating drought resilience, while IC-305477 and IC-328020 had higher DSI values, indicating higher susceptibility. This index, introduced by Fischer and Maurer (1978), remains a robust tool for screening genotype response under differential moisture regimes.

4. CONCLUSION

The present study demonstrated significant genotypic variability in response to drought stress across a range of morpho-physiological and yield-related traits under both normal (E1) and late sown (E2) conditions. Moisture stress markedly affected key developmental traits such as plant height, days to maturity, reproductive duration, and pod number, while relative water content (RWC) and test weight remained relatively stable, indicating their potential as drought-resilient traits.

Genotypes such as K-850 and ICC 4958 emerged as promising candidates for drought tolerance, exhibiting stable performance and lower drought susceptibility indices (DSI) under stress conditions. Conversely, genotypes like IC-328020 and IC-305477 were more vulnerable to water deficit, as reflected by their high DSI values and yield reduction. Early flowering and maturity observed in IC-305593 suggest its potential as a drought escape genotype, a

valuable trait in terminal drought-prone environments.

The findings emphasize the importance of selecting genotypes with favorable morpho-physiological traits and yield stability under stress, which can contribute to breeding programs aimed at improving drought resilience. The study also reinforces the value of evaluating germplasm under varied sowing conditions to identify genotypes with consistent performance, aiding in the development of climate-resilient cultivars.

DISCLAIMER (ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE)

Author(s) hereby declares that NO generative AI technologies such as Large Language Models (ChatGPT, COPILOT, etc) and text-to-image generators have been used during writing or editing of this manuscript.

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

REFERENCES

- Arnon, R., Crisp, E., Kelley, R., Ellison, G. W., Myers, L. W., & Tourtellotte, W. W. (1980). Anti-ganglioside antibodies in multiple sclerosis. *Journal of the Neurological Sciences*, 46(2), 179-186.
- Devi, M. J., Sinclair, T. R., Chen, P., & Carter, T. E. (2014). Evaluation of elite southern maturity soybean breeding lines for drought tolerance. *Agronomy Journal*, 106(6), 1947-1954.
- Farooq, M., Wahid, A., Kobayashi, N., Fujita, D., & Basra, S. M. A. (2009). Plant drought stress: Effects, mechanisms and management. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development*, 29(1), 185-212.
- Fischer, R. A., & Maurer, R. (1978). Drought resistance in spring wheat cultivars. I. Grain yield responses. *Australian Journal of Agricultural Research*, 29(5), 897-912.
- Iqbal, M., Sher, A., Sattar, A., & Ali, L. (2019). Physiological and morphological evaluation of chickpea genotypes under drought stress. *Legume Research*, 42(3), 411-417.
- Jukanti, A. K., Gaur, P. M., Gowda, C. L., & Chibbar, R. N. (2012). Nutritional quality and health benefits of chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.): A review. *British Journal of Nutrition*, 108(S1), S11-S26.
- Khan, H. R., Link, W., Hocking, T. J., & Stoddard, F. L. (2010). Evaluation of physiological traits for improving drought tolerance in faba bean (*Vicia faba* L.). *Plant and Soil*, 339(1-2), 479-496.
- Kumar, J., Abbo, S., & Sharma, K. D. (2012). Genetics and genomics of chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.): Legume perspectives. *Plant Breeding*, 131(3), 289-303.
- Pandey, G. K., Sharma, A., & Kumar, D. (2015). Impact of moisture stress on seed development and yield in chickpea genotypes. *Indian Journal of Plant Physiology*, 20(4), 349-353.
- Passioura, J. B. (2012). Phenotyping for drought tolerance in grain crops: When is it useful to breeders? *Functional Plant Biology*, 39(11), 851-859.
- Reddy, T. Y., Reddy, V. R., & Anbumozhi, V. (2021). Crop responses to drought and implications for crop modeling: A review. *Agricultural Water Management*, 82(1-2), 15-33.
- Sharma, S., & Sharma, R. (2020). Chickpea economy in India. Chickpea: crop wild relatives for enhancing genetic gains, 225-250.
- Sharma, S., Yadav, R. K., & Singh, N. P. (2016). Genetic variation for drought tolerance traits in chickpea. *Journal of Food Legumes*, 29(4), 298-302.
- Sivasakthi, K., Tharanya, M., & Thilagavathi, M. (2017). Morpho-physiological responses of chickpea genotypes under moisture stress. *Legume Research*, 40(2), 304-308.
- Tuberosa, R. (2012). Phenotyping for drought tolerance of crops in the genomics era. *Frontiers in Physiology*, 3, 347.

Varshney, R. K., Thudi, M., Nayak, S. N., Gaur, P. M., Kashiwagi, J., Krishnamurthy, L., ... & Hoisington, D. A. (2014). Genomic

strategies for improving grain yield in chickpea under drought. *Plant, Cell & Environment*, 37(3), 683–694.

Disclaimer/Publisher's Note: The statements, opinions and data contained in all publications are solely those of the individual author(s) and contributor(s) and not of the publisher and/or the editor(s). This publisher and/or the editor(s) disclaim responsibility for any injury to people or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions or products referred to in the content.

© Copyright (2025): Author(s). The licensee is the journal publisher. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Peer-review history:

The peer review history for this paper can be accessed here:

<https://prh.globalpresshub.com/review-history/2025>